

FORMATION OF ANALOGIES USING LEXICAL MEANS (ON THE EXAMPLE OF THE WORKS OF UTKIR HOSHIMOV)

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Annotatsiya: В статье рассматривается вопрос создания сравнений с помощью лексических средств, что является одним из способов выражения экспрессивности в художественном тексте, и поясняется на примерах из литературных произведений.

Annotation: This article is devoted to the issue of creating similes using lexical means, which is one of the possibilities for expressing expressiveness in a literary text, and is explained with examples from literary works.

Kalit so'zlar: аналогия, лексические средства, грамматические средства, эмоционально-выразительная выразительность, аффективность.

Keywords: analogy, lexical means, grammatical means, emotional-expressiveness, affectivity.

It is known that the richness of a language is not determined only by the abundance of words in its lexicon. The richness of a language is determined not only by the numerical abundance of words, but also by their diverse meanings, the expression of the most subtle shades of meaning, the presence of synonymous words, similes, and colorful stylistic features.

Language, an important means of communication between people, is a complex phenomenon that not only performs a communicative function, but also has the power to perform nominative and expressive functions. "The fact that language has a nominative and expressive function is reflected in the elements of language, especially words."¹ Expressive-emotional can be created on the basis of similes, stylistic synonyms, some stylistically limited lexical layers and phraseologisms. The role and status of similes in increasing the expressiveness of the language of the literary text is measured by their role in ensuring the individuality of speech, as well as in individualizing the speech of the characters.

The expression of simile occurs within the text. Because while some writers liken one object or event to another object or event, another writer or poet compares the same object or event to a completely different object or event.

The means of creating similes in sources are divided into two groups:

1. Lexical means.
2. Grammatical means.²

We can include words like *kabi, singari, qadar, yang'lig', bamisoli, bamisli, misoli, misli, monand, xuddi, naq, go'yo, teng, o'xshatmoq, eslatmoq, aynan* in lexical means. *-day, -dek, -dayin,*

¹ Haydarov A. Konnotativ ma'noning nutqda voqelanishi // Til tizimi va nutqiy faoliyat. Respublika ilmiy-amaliy anjumani materiallari. – Samarqand, 2010. 98-100-betlar.

² Karimov S. Badiiy uslub va tilning ifoda tasvir vositalari. – Samarqand, 1994. – B. 18.
Qo'ng'urov R. O'zbek tilining tasviriy vositalari – Toshkent: Fan, 1977. – B. 41

-namo, -simon, -ona, -omuz, -cha, -larcha, -chalik, -chasiga and suffixes are considered grammatical devices.

The similes used in the story “Two times two is five” by Uzbek literature’s unique style Utkir Hoshimov use lexical devices such as *o’xshab*, *xuddi*, *naq*, *qatori*.

One of the most commonly used lexical devices in similes in the story is the word like (*o’xshab*):

*O’n kungacha dakang varrakka o’xshab lapanglab turgan.*³ (For ten days, your body was limping like a kite.)

Also, the word “*o’xshab*” is used in various forms in the work:

– Ajab qipsiz! – dedi kulishga urinib, o’zi kulyapti-yu, afti xuddi yig’layotgan odamnikiga *o’xshaydi*. (“You’re amazing!” he said, trying to laugh, but it sounded **like** someone was crying)⁴ (195-b)

Shunaqangi shirinki, iris ishkaladga o’xshaydi. (*It’s so sweet it looks like chocolate.*) (213-b.)

The following forms of the word “*o’xshab*” can also be observed in the story:

Shodivoy ham menga o’xshagan bittayu-bitta o’g’il. (*Shodivoy is an only son, just like me.*) (208-b.)

– *O’zing ahmoq!* – *Shodivoyning ham jazavasi qo’zib ketdi.* – *Eshakka o’xshagan befahm. Qamatmayman!* (*You idiot! - Shodivoy also got angry. – Stupid like a donkey. I will not put you in prison!*) (377-b.)

Oyog’ida Rais buva kiyib yuraliganiga o’xshash jigarrang etik, qo’lida panshaxa! (*On his feet are brown boots like to those worn by the Rais, and in his hand is a panshakha!*) (228-b.)

You can also see that the word “*xuddi*” (the same, as) is actively used in the story as a simile:

Hovliga kirib, angrayib qoldim. Xuddi tomoshabog’ning o’zi! (*I entered the courtyard and gasped. It the same a place to watch!*) (212-b.)

When forming a simile using the word “*xuddi*”, one can observe the use of the suffixes “-dek” and “-day” together with the word “*xuddi*”:

– *Do-o-od!* – *xotin shunaqangi yo’g’on ovozdahayqirdiki, xuddi stansiyadagi teplovoz gudok chalgandek ikki qulog’im bitib qoldi.* (*Do-o-od! The woman screamed so loudly that I lost hearing in both ears, as a train whistle at a station.*) (214-b.)

Mashina to’ntarilib yotsa, g’alati bo’larkan. Xuddi oyog’i osmondan bo’lib qolgan qo’ng’izdek. (*It would be weird if the car was upside down, like a beetle with its hind legs hanging in the sky.*) (234-b.)

Or,

Ikkala eshikni qarsillatib yopdi-da, xuddi ming yil shopirlik qilgan taksichilarday ishonch bilan motorni gurillatib yubordi. (*He slammed the two doors shut and roared the engine with the same confidence as taxi drivers who had been driving for a thousand years.*) (225-b.)

There are also places in the work where, although not very productive, similes are created using the word “*naq*”:

Hovlimas, naq jannatning o’zi! (*The courtyard is like paradise itself!*) (273-b.)

³ Hoshimov O’. Tanlangan asarlar. II jild. – Toshkent: Sharq, 2009. –B. 191.

⁴ The examples are taken from the source above.

In the story, the word "naq" is used together with pronouns like "o'zginasi" or "o'zi":
Naq tosh yo'lining o'zginasi! (It's **like** a rocky road!) (252-b.)

In general, similes used appropriately serve to make speech more figurative, effective, and expressive. Similes play a special role in ensuring the uniqueness of Utkir Hoshimov's style. The similes used in the writer's story "Two times two is five" use lexical devices such as "o'xshab", "xuddi", "naq" and the word "o'xshab" is used more actively than other lexical devices.

Adabiyotlar, References, Литературы:

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